

From knowing to showing: Using marking tasks to demonstrate information literacy in practice

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FORMAT

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ABSTRACT

Search engines are frequently used and trusted information resources (European Commission, 2016). Therefore, the competent handling of search engines is critical for contemporary education and citizenship (OECD, 2021; UNESCO, 2021). The issue becomes even more pressing in light of a global pandemic which fuels the need for reliable information (Dadaczynski et al., 2021). Information literacy regarding search engines has often been examined using questionnaires with items on knowledge and information-seeking behavior (Schilling & Applegate, 2012; Taylor & Dalal, 2017; Timmers & Glas, 2010). However, addressing factual and procedural knowledge solely with questions is constrained to cognition and does not provide evidence of literate information behavior (Nierenberg, Låg, & Dahl, 2021).

Therefore, it is suggested to amend such questionnaires with tasks that require subjects to apply and demonstrate their knowledge on a behavioral stage. Information behavior research is shaped by qualitative methods like interviews, content analysis, and observations (Julien & O'Brien, 2014). However, those studies are often limited in their validity due to small sample sizes. Regarding these shortcomings, our presentation aims to introduce marking tasks as a quantitative approach to investigating information literacy on a behavioral stage. Furthermore, we would like to conceptually discuss how to better inform information literacy research.

We define marking tasks as task-based questionnaire items where subjects are presented with clickable illustrations, e.g., screenshots of search systems. Depending on the research question, subjects are asked to mark certain elements, e.g., by clicking on them. Success rates can be calculated as the ratio of correct versus incorrect markings a person made and indicate to what extent subjects can demonstrate their knowledge.

To study user understanding of search engine result pages (SERPs), we integrated marking tasks in two surveys with samples representative of the German Internet population. In one study, subjects were instructed to distinguish between sponsored (ads) and organic results on SERP screenshots (Lewandowski, Kerkmann, Rümmele, & Sünkler, 2018), while the other study focused on search engine optimization (SEO) and on user abilities to associate SEO with organic results (Schultheiß & Lewandowski, 2021b). In addition to the marking tasks, the questionnaires included self-assessments of information literacy and knowledge-based questions on ads and SEO. The results of the surveys informed two follow-up user studies that reused the marking tasks (Schultheiß, Häußler, & Lewandowski, 2022; Schultheiß & Lewandowski, 2021a). Overall, the results indicate that users are confident about their information literacy. Still, the majority proves knowledge gaps and cannot reliably demonstrate their claimed literacy in practice, which is a common discrepancy, as noted by Mahmood (2016).

The presentation aims to open a conceptual discussion about the possibilities of using marking tasks in diverse contexts. Based on insights into the authors' research, challenges and good practices are provided. With our conceptual discussion, we hope to encourage researchers to reflect on methodological questions concerning information literacy research, and to contribute an innovative approach to investigating user understanding that underlies information behavior.

KEYWORDS

Information literacy, research methods, search engines, marking tasks

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